

CDA of Bhutto's Speeches: A Study of Language of Politicians in Pakistan

Tariq Ali¹, Saba Rafi², Tehreema Hassan³

Abstract

The current study aims to analyze language used by Pakistani politicians while applying Fairclough's CDA model. This study provides theoretical overview how politicians project their ideology while employing certain devices in their political discourse. The research examines the strategies such as emotional exploitation, three words theory, art of spin, repetition of linguistic choices like pronouns and figures of speech as employed by politicians particularly by Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto in his speeches. This article reveals how he applies the rhetorical and persuasive language to convince his audience while provoking their emotions to achieve his political aims. The study provides a vivid picture of language used by politicians and recommends future researchers to explore other aspects of political genre in Pakistan.

Keywords: Emotional Exploitation, Three sword theory, Art of spin, Linguistic Choices, Language as a power and Ideology

1. Introduction

Language serves as a tool and weapon simultaneously. It is source of expression of the inner of any one and it also becomes a source of power. If language is used wisely, it becomes a source of pleasure for the speaker and the listener as well but if it is used unwisely it may bring problem for the both. It's been used for centuries, not only by human beings but by non-humans also. People from all the walks of life use it to solve their relevant issues and problems and at the same time to create the issues and problems. It gives meanings and shapes to the feelings of the people. People who use it to express themselves according to their own point of view, they sometime don't know that language is such a power which expresses inner self of those who use it to express themselves. The study of the relationship between language and political use of language has drawn much attention in the linguistic domain (e.g., Chilton, 2004; Fairclough, 2000; Wilson, 1990). For instance, Wilson (1990) argued that metaphor can perform multi roles; such as to think, evaluate, and act in political discourse. Among all the people who use language, the politicians are those who utilize it to get their own targets, aim, objects etc.

Language of politicians includes the language in newspapers, radio and T.V. The speeches of the politicians at public gatherings may also be included in politicians' language. The researcher has selected to analyze the political language because the statements published in newspapers, broadcast on radio or telecast on T.V are well prepared and organized whereas the speeches at public gatherings are mostly extempore and project the speaker's ideology more vividly and in an explicit way. The reasons to select Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's speeches are:

- Bhutto was very popular among the masses and his popularity is still at peak.
- He got Prime Ministership and Presidentship and his regime was overthrown.

After his regime was overthrown he faced legal suits and finally death sentence. The researcher did his level best not to be partial and as a neutral observer has conducted his research without any bias. The researcher has analyzed politicians' language to find out how the politicians of Pakistan (especially Bhutto) employ different devices to project their ideology through their speeches and get particular objectives.

1.1. Significance of the Study

So, the present study will definitely help the masses to understand and analyze politicians' language in a new way. This article will help the masses to take a decision about casting their vote to the right person. This article may also be helpful for the masses to understand the ideology presented in the language of politicians whether the politicians have some ideology or not.

2. Literature Review

The researcher selected Bhutto's speeches because he was the strongest politician with a strong ideology and secondly Bhutto's speeches and language are still being used as a model. In the light of this article, the language of all the politicians can be observed and understood. This article is an attempt to analyze, unfold, decode, interpret and illustrate the language as used by politicians in Pakistan. This article gives a theoretical overview of research on political discourse with particular regard to use of metaphors in political discourse, art of spin, rhetorical devices to tempt the public and the use of personal pronoun and repetition. The discourse of political demagogue has been prime focus in the earlier studies (e.g., Beard, 2000; Chilton, 2004; Chilton & Schäffner, 1997; De Landtsheer, 1998; Gastil, 1992). The recent studies have focused on the role of metaphor in political discourse (e.g., De Landtsheer, 1998; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980a), how rhetorical devices are employed by politician to invite audience applause (e.g., J. W. Atkinson, 1983; Bull & Fetzer, 2006; Duszak, 2002) and the use of pronoun (e.g., Bull & Fetzer, 2006; Duszak, 2002;

¹Lecturer in English, Khwaja Fareed University of Engineering and IT, RYK, Pakistan, Email: Tariq.ali@kfueit.edu.pk

²Lecturer in English, Govt Girls college, RYK, Pakistan, Email: Saba_rafi1@yahoo.com

³Assistant Professor of English, Government Graduate College for Women, Rahim Yar Khan, Pakistan, Email: tehremahassan@gmail.com

Fairclough, 2001; Gastil, 1992; Wilson, 1990). While examining the above mentioned aspects of research on political discourse, the present article is designed to tempt the other researchers to use these theoretical frameworks in their researches. Now the researcher will elaborate the terms Discourse, Interactional Discourse and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA).

2.1. Discourse

The term 'Discourse' means the use of language in context. Zelling Harris (1957) was the first person who used the term 'Discourse Analysis' (DA) in his analysis of an advertisement. He interpreted two possible areas of discourse analysis: firstly, descriptive linguistics; secondly, correlating culture and language (Harris, 1957) as cited in Cook, 1989). DA considers how language users make sense of text; understands what speakers mean despite what they say; recognizes connected discourse as opposed to jumbled or incoherent one; and effectively takes part in the complex activity called conversation (Yule, 1996).

2.2. Interactional Discourse (ID)

Discourse analysis, conversation analysis and interaction analysis are closely connected in linguistic investigation of a language. (Nunan, 1992) states that the distinction between them is that of emphasis rather than category e.g., discourse analysis studies textual factors such as cohesive devices and the ways in which speech acts like requesting, inviting and apologizing are performed and interpreted within coherent discourse. Conversational analysis investigates turn-taking, repair strategies, the resolution of ambiguity, speaker selection and topical relevance. Discourse analysis is concerned with rhetorical elements while conversation analysis with social activities and interaction analysis with linguistic and non-linguistic aspects of spoken language.

2.3. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)

CDA is a branch of Discourse Analysis. In CDA the term critical, is a theoretical concept. The term shows that the researcher must bring to light the ideology hidden in the discourse. The term 'Critical' (and the associated term critique) refers to human matters, interconnections and chains of cause and effect that may be distorted out of vision (Fairclough, 1998). (Gramsci, 1971b) and (Althusser, 1971a) both have emphasized the importance of ideology and reinforce their social structural relations with modern societies. Critical Linguists / discourse theorists have developed a radically different form of analysis which inflects the term discourse differently (Mills, 2002).

3. Research Methodology

Qualitative Data of the present study has been presented through words and analyzed through thematic exploration. Therefore, method has been consciously manipulated for the study in hand. The figure below shows the study depends on eclectic method. The qualities benefited from the approach are encircled in the given figure.

(Adapted from (O'Leary, 2005).

The study is Qualitative as the analysis has been performed by the interpretative and thematic exploration by applying Fairclough's model.

3.1. Framework of the Study

The theories of Althusser, Gramsci, Foucault and Fairclough have been applied to analyze the data. Especially Fairclough's three-dimensional theory as a model has been applied. The researcher has considered the theories of Foucault (1981) Althusser (1971) Gramsci (1980) Sara Mill (1996) and Norman Fairclough (1995).

The Three-Dimensional Analysis of discourse [adapted from Fairclough, Norman. 1992. *Discourse and Social Change* (Page 93, Figure 5-2). Cambridge: Polity Press]

3.2. Data Collection

Data has been collected from internet and a book named “Bhutto ki Awaz”(Ujin & Goundi, 1988).

In the following section, this article is divided into six sections. 1. Emotional exploitation, 2. Repetition of Three-word theory. 3. Art of spin. 4. Linguistic choices 5. Language as a power, 6. Ideology.

4. Data Analysis and Findings

Here the researcher has discussed and described above mentioned six points, analyzing Bhutto’s speeches while applying Critical Discourse Analysis of speeches of Bhutto to public gatherings at different occasions.

4.1. Emotional Exploitation

Emotions are a great power to force or derive people in any direction. Sometime emotions become weak point of someone. Emotions can be used to use people. And language is the best source to express and exploit emotions. Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary defines language as... “The system of communication in speech & writing that is used by people of a particular country” (Hornby, 2007).

We use language to encode and decode information and it takes us to “Natural Languages” especially to human beings. Language is a cognitive faculty of human and it creates and uses language in an appropriate way. Language is also regarded an organized system of symbols with semantics and logical meanings. If we do analyze language technically, it may be regarded as a “thought” without communication or expression. According to Western Philosophy, language is related to “reason”. According to Ancient Greek Philosophy the word “logos” was used for language or speech and reason while the philosopher Hobbes (1962) used the word “speech” as reason.

Bhutto assures the people that PPP will be with the masses and calls them force. He reminds the masses that being in majority they deserve to rule the country. People’s curiosity about language, its operation and origin take us not only to Plato and Aristotle but also to Greek and Indian philosophers. The vitality of language is determined by various

roles of language in human life and it is the only tool to express human thoughts. For example, at present we can find a lot of languages in the world, expressing thoughts, literature and ways of life. Today language is the cause or source of progress and prosperity in the world.

Original Text	Translation	Item Analysis
آپ کی اپنی جماعت پاکستان پیپلز پارٹی ہمیشہ عوامی قوتوں کے ساتھ رہے گی۔ یہ قوتیں یہاں کے مزدور، کسان، طالب علم اور غریب لوگ ہیں۔ یہی اس ملک کے نمائندے ہیں۔ یہ ملک انہی لوگوں کا ہے اور یہی اس کی تقدیر کے مالک ہیں تاکہ چند لوگ۔	Your own party, Pakistan Peoples' Party (PPP), will always remain with the public forces. The labourers, farmers, students, and the poor people are the real forces. These people are the real representatives of the country. This country belongs to these people who are the owner of its destiny, nor a few people.	Created identity. Use of pronoun. Personal to public. Created Identity. Hegemony. Exploitation to win sympathies. Sisterlike relationship.

“There is the importance we attach to language as a means of understanding ourselves and our society and resolving some of the problems and tensions that arise from human interactions” Crystal (1991).

4.2. Three Word Theory

The politicians always employ certain devices and tactics to inculcate ideas. K. Atkinson and Atkinson (2003) considers it a list of Three Word Theory,

“Repetition and contrast are frequently used together as a rhetorical device.”

This list of three is very attractive because it exists in different cultures and gives a sense of compactness and unity. For example, Atkinson mentions the slogan of Labour Party “Education, Education, Education”. Similarly, the Quaid-e-Azam raised a slogan “Work, Work and Work”. In this slogan we find a repetition and it motivates the masses. The Quaid had another slogan “Unity, Faith, Discipline”. In this slogan we find a contrast and not repetition. In this connection, Zulifkar Ali also raised a slogan “Roti, Kapra aur Makan”. The American president Borak Hussain Obama had a slogan “Change we Need”. It is another example of the three-word slogan or theory.

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
عوام کو بیدار کیا، ان کی سوچوں کا زاویہ تبدیل کیا اور ان کی پرکھ میں انقلاب برپا کر دیا پارٹی کی جدوجہد اسی مقصد کے تحت ہوئی۔ بچے بچوں کو تعلیم دلایں۔ انہیں صحت کی سہولتیں میسر ہوں ہر تہ کو مناسب جگہ ہو وہ لوگ آج سن لیں جن کے پاس کھانے کو خوراک نہیں، پہننے کو کپڑے نہیں اور رہنے کو مکان نہیں۔	Awakened the people, changed their way of thinking and revolutionized their way of judgment. This was the purpose of the struggle of the party. Get their children educated, have health facilities, have suitable or proper place to live. Listen, those who have no food to eat, no clothes to wear, no house to live in.	Three words theory Bhutto's slogan Three words slogan. Sisterlike relationship. Three words slogan.

These slogans are not merely the words but have a deep philosophy in them. The real importance of these words is in the way they are uttered. The way the speakers use them to exploit by employing conversational tactics such as pitch, rhythm, loudness, intonation, context and the situation, has a vital role in casting spell on the masses.

4.3. The Art of Spin

The politicians who present facts to the media are considered as Spin Doctors by the public relation experts in America. The word “spin” has been taken from baseball in America (and current in Pakistan). The word “spin” is a

pitcher's technique (in Pakistan bowler's technique) to deceive the opponents. In Pakistan politicians use this technique to deceive and exploit the audience or opponents.

The art of spin is used in speech by giving different coloring or by targeting a figure in different ways. So, spin is often used to get credit or blame others. So, these things, credit or blame, are achieved by either emphasizing or by minimizing the role.

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
مجھے فخر ہے کہ طلباء میرے ساتھ ہیں کیا ہوا جو انہیں ووٹ کا حق حاصل نہیں۔ ملک و قوم کا مستقبل تو انہی کے ہاتھوں میں ہے۔ ہم سرمایہ داروں اور ان کے گماشتوں کے خلاف لڑ رہے ہیں	I feel proud that students are with me. So, what if students don't have right to vote, Country and Nation's Future is in their hands. We are fighting against the capitalists and their cat's paws,	Art of Spin. Power of language. Art of spin.
آپ کی کوششوں سے طوفانوں کے ریلے، سچائی کا قحط، یہ جمود، یہ سقوط سب آنے والے سال کی برق میں جل کے خاک ہو جائیگا۔ آج حکمرانی کے تخت پر وہ لوگ قابض ہیں جن کو عوام سے دور کی نسبت نہیں۔	With your own efforts, these currents of storms, the famine of truth, this inertia, this stress, all these will end up in the lightening of coming years. Today those people, who don't have even the remote relation with the public, are occupying the throne.	Art of spin. Art of spin.
پاکستان کے عوام جمہوریت کے لیے جدوجہد کر رہے ہیں۔ جمہوریت میں لوگ اپنی رائے کا اظہار کرتے ہیں۔	The public of Pakistan is struggling for democracy. People express their opinions in democracy.	General to particular. Art of spin.
ہم سرمایہ داروں اور جاگیرداروں کو ختم کر دیں گے۔	We will shun off capitalists and feudalists.	Art of spin.
اے علامہ اقبال دیکھو میں نے تمہاری دنیا کے لوگوں کو جگا دیا ہے۔	O Allama Iqbal! Behold, I have awakened the people of your world.	Use of Apostrophe. Art of spin.

4.4. Linguistic Choices

Technically human language is regarded as a "thought" even without communication or expression. According to Western Philosophy, language is related to "reason" and it is human way of using symbols. According to Ancient Greek Philosophy the word "logos" was a term for language or speech and reason while the philosopher Hobbes (1962) regarded the word "speech" as reason. This Language or speech as a reason is used in variety of ways. It's

used to develop certain connections between the speaker and the listeners in the form of sisterlike relation, use of pronoun and metaphor.

4.4.1. The Sisterlike Relationship

The politicians while using the political strategies develop a relationship between themselves and audience. During a speech they construct an imaginary community where they and the audience are the members. This relationship is regarded a “synthetic sisterhood” by Atkinson (2009). Brown and Levinson (1987) write, “This kind of friendly behaviour, the signaling of closeness and interest in another person, is sometimes known as being positively polite.”

This type of relationship demands the attention of the speaker and the audience. The politeness from the speaker contributes in developing an informal relationship.

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
اپنے بچوں کو تعلیم دلائیں۔ انہیں صحت کی سہولتیں میسر ہوں ہر نے کو مناسب جگہ ہو	They get their children educated; have health facilities, and proper place to live.	Three words slogan. Sisterlike relationship.
کیا یہ لوگ زندگی کی آسائشوں کے حقدار نہیں۔ یہ درد اور تکلیف محسوس نہیں کرتے۔ کیا ان کی کوئی خواہشات نہیں ہیں۔	Do they not deserve the luxuries of life? Do they not feel pain and suffering? Do they have not desires?	Exploitation. Emotional Urge. Sisterlike relationship.
میں عوام کی اکثریت کا نمائندہ ہوں اور وہ ایک معمولی اقلیت کے نمائندے ہیں۔	I represent majority of people and they (opponent) are of usual minority.	Use of Figurative language. Sisterlike relationship.
پاکستان کے عوام جمہوریت چاہتے ہیں اور ہم نے اس کے لیے جدوجہد کی۔	People of Pakistan want democracy and we've struggled for it.	Use of pronoun. Sisterlike relation.

4.4.2. The Shift from Personal to Public & Public to Personal

The politicians sometimes shift from personal to public and vice versa, during a speech This process of shifting gives birth to personalities. The politicians use different expressions, gestures and language in different styles to establish a synthetic or artificial personality. While shifting, the speakers adopt different behaviours, sometimes normal, humble and sometimes authoritative.

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
آپ کی اپنی جماعت	Your own party, Pakistan	Created identity.
پاکستان پیپلز پارٹی	People's Party, will always remain with the public forces.	Use of pronoun. Personal to public.
ہمیشہ عوامی قوتوں کے ساتھ رہے گی۔		

4.4.3. The Role of Pronouns in the Political language

The pronouns have prominent and indispensable role in the language of politicians. They are mostly used to persuade or address the audience. With the appropriate use of pronouns, the speaker can easily influence the audience and can get the required result. For instance, the use of 1st person pronouns “we, our, us” gives a sense of sharing or collectiveness. By the use of the 1st person pronoun, the speaker tries to persuade the listeners according to his/her point of view. While the use of 2nd person pronouns “you, your, yours” gives a sense that the listeners are being addressed. So, with the right use of pronouns the politicians draw the attention of the public and get their sympathies and easily win their favour.

4.4.4. Use of Figurative Language

4.4.4.1. The Power of Metaphors

Beard (2000) writes, “Both politicians, and those who report politics, use these metaphors.”

Metaphors refer to when a word or a phrase is used which establishes a comparison between one idea and another.

“Recent work on semantics in English has investigated the place of metaphor in everyday speech.”

Goatly (1997)

Metaphors are deeply embedded in the way we construct the world around us and the way the world is constructed for us by the people in our surrounding. Two common sources of metaphors in politics are “sports” and “war”. Both these sources involve physical contest of some sort. For instance, in Britain, boxing metaphor is particularly common, which conveys a sense of aggression and toughness. Lakoff and Johnson (1980b) write about the British Election of 1997.

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
آپ کی اپنی جماعت پاکستان پیپلز پارٹی ہمیشہ عوامی قوتوں کے ساتھ رہے گی۔ ہم سرمایہ داروں اور ان کے گماشتوں کے خلاف لڑ رہے ہیں پاکستان کے عوام جمہوریت چاہتے ہیں اور ہم نے اس کے لیے جدوجہد کی۔ رجعت پسند ہم پر انتہا پسندی کا الزام لگاتے ہیں۔ ہمیں یہ تسلیم کرنے میں کوئی جھجک نہیں کہ ہم انتہا پسند ہیں۔	Your own party, Pakistan People’s Party, will always remain with the public forces. We are fighting against the capitalists and their cat’s paws, People of Pakistan want democracy and we struggled for it. The optimists blame us of extremism and tell the masses that extremism is an unwise and harmful policy. We don’t hesitate in admitting that we are extremists.	Created identity. Use of pronoun. Personal to public. Art of spin. Use of pronoun. Use of pronoun. Sisterlike relation. Use of pronoun. Sisterlike relationship.

“When the British Election of 1997 was announced, one newspaper had the headline. *The Gloves are off, suggesting not boxing, but a bare-knuckle fight.*”

Similarly, in the USA, metaphors for baseball are abound in politics i.e, “a whole new ball game,” “a ball park figure”, “to play ball,” or to be “back at first base” can be presented as a few examples. In the same way the politicians in Pakistan, usually use “cricket metaphors”. For instance, after his being acquitted from the cases, Asif Ali Zardari gave a statement in the newspapers that if the next general elections are held fair, PPP will perform in the style of Shahid Afridi. Gibbs Jr (1994) points out that metaphors from sports and war are:

“not rhetorical devices for talking about politics, for the exemplify how people ordinarily conceive of politics ----- for instance metaphors from sports and war often delude people into believing that negotiation and compromise are forbidden by the rules.”

In this way, it can be said that because so much language which surrounds political issues is rooted in metaphors of war, contest or sport --- that if we had not been consciously aware of these roots, we would have then no idea that politics could be anything other than confrontation. Sometimes metaphors are used to replace the name of something with something else that is connected to it, without being the whole thing. For instance, the US President, Government and advisors are sometimes replaced by the much simpler term “The White House”. Similarly, in Britain, the British Royal Family is replaced by “The Buckingham Palace.” In Pakistan, any announcement on behalf of President or Prime minister or foreign office is announced as “The Islamabad said ...”

Metaphors affect the audience’s perception of and attitude to the original thing. For instance, if a US politician says that the white House today threatened Iran with military action, here the metaphor “the White House” replaces the president of USA and his advisors, and.

“When analyses are used, therefore, the reader must not just accept them but must evaluate their strength as a price of argument.” Beard (2000)

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
اے لوگو! ظلم کی اس لمبی رات کو ہمیشہ کے اجالے میں بدل ڈالو آج یہ چند کیڑے ملکی دولت کے تمام تر ذرائع پر قبضہ کئے جا رہے ہیں۔	O people! Change this long night of cruelty into the everlasting brightness at last. Today these worms are gradually capturing all the resources of country’s wealth.	Use of figurative language. Use of figurative language.

5.4.4.2. The Role of Metaphors

“Metaphoric expressions tend to be organized in chain across texts”. Koller (2003)

However, a question is raised what roles the metaphoric expressions play in different parts of a text as well as in relation to each other, or what cognitive scenarios these expressions evolve from their chains.

Halliday (1978) distinguishes between the following three meta functions of language: in its interpersonal function, language serves to constitute and negotiate social identities and relations; at the level of clause, this function results in the clause being “organized as an interactive event [in which] the speaker adopts for himself a particular speech role, and in doing so assigns to the listener a complementary role which he wishes him to adopt in his turn” Halliday (1994), Finally, the textual function of language is defined as “creating relevance to context” Halliday (1994), or providing cohesion to a text.

We apply the above mentioned meta-functions of language to metaphors in the following lines.

Applying the first Hallidayan function of language to metaphor, we can quote here (Norman, 1989) Fairclough as he notes “metaphor can help to convey ideology”.

“Metaphors [...] highlight and make coherent certain aspects of our experience [...] metaphors may create realities for us, especially social realities”. Lakoff and Johnson (1980b).

It shows that both Fairclough and Lakoff hint at metaphors’ role in constituting social identities and relations.

Applying the second Hallidayan function of language to metaphor, we can say that metaphor works at conceptual level. It entails that metaphor-as-exchange functions to construct the position of text producer and text recipient. It, thus, establishes a relation between them, and this relation is established by the text producer alone. To proceed further, we can say that language can be seen as an ideational device that conveys representational meaning. Thus, it helps to construct reality from a particular point of view.

Applying the third Hallidayan function of language to metaphors, it can be said that it pertains to its linguistic reflection as metaphoric expression. Metaphor as message thus exhibits some form of organization giving the text the status of a communicative event.

Apart from the above-mentioned discussion, it seems important to point out that metaphoric expressions most importantly play out in chains across the text. Halliday (1978) states that text is “actualized meaning potential”; text is like a syntagmatic chain of slots to be filled with paradigmatic choices. What fillers are chosen depends as much on the text producer’s perceived identity as discourse participant as it does on the goals, he/she wishes to achieve with that particular choice, and on his/her anticipation of reader’s responses. These mechanisms determining the choice of fillers again reflect the interpersonal, ideational and textual functions. The filler slots can be lexical, grammatical or stylistic. Metaphoric expressions may cluster in different slots of the text, and their clustering in different slots make them perform different functions. For instance, when metaphoric expressions cluster at the beginning of a text, they actualize an ideational function by introducing the topic as defined by a particular metaphor. Such an initial cognitive representation helps to set the agenda the author / speaker has in his / her mind. When metaphors bundle in mid-text, on the other hand, they realize an interpersonal function by arguing the authors’ case. Finally, when metaphors cluster towards the end of the text, they work interpersonally as well: by helping author/speaker to re-instantiate and reinforce his/her particular metaphoric construction (s) and this drive the point home to their readers / audience. Thus, metaphors with end weight very much serve a persuasive function.

The metaphoric usages are a byproduct of the speakers’ idiosyncratic communication style. When these byproducts occur in clusters, they suggest that the author/speaker wants to present an alternative interpretation of the topic. For this purpose, he/she may use a super ordinate metaphor or even use various subordinate metaphors to give an interpretation of the super ordinate metaphor. In such cases, it seems likely that the author/speaker may continue using the metaphors for a number of sentences, enough to produce a recognizable cluster. Thus, the cluster represents the intent of the author/speaker to explain a topic.

5.5. Language as a Power

The Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary defines power as ----- “The ability or opportunity to do something or strength or influence in a particular area of activity” Sally Wehmeier (2009).

So, the term power is generally linked with physical strength and its absence means the absence of that strength. The holders of power can work wonders in both positive and negative sense. In this scenario the politicians use this power in such a way that the individuals or masses who are being victimized cannot understand the motives of their political leaders in their activities they are performing. Some politicians use power of language by creating such atmosphere that the masses consider that the things are going in the favour of the people but actually the politicians fulfill their own objectives.

In the light of above mentioned thought, the Modernists assert that power is a vague term which cannot be associated with a single quality. They say that power can be produced from different sources i.e., weapons or the ownership of some production. These theorists hold this belief that power has many dimensions such as class, group, race, ethics, gender and religion etc. Power is a multi-dimensional phenomenon. In this connection, the complexity in the modern concept of power can be seen through Foucault’s phrase about power. “A Net-Like Organization” K. Atkinson and Atkinson (2003) say,

“Power in Foucault’s view ... is a force and an effect which exists and circulates in a web of social interaction”. So in the light of modern concept power is something that is exercised through a net like organization and individuals circulate not only in this organization but also exercise or utilize it .Foucault (1980) says that the individuals are not only its inert or consenting target but are also the elements of its articulation. In other words, individuals are the vehicles of power, not its point of application. In the light of Foucault’s definition, individuals are tools to utilize power and they are medium to use power.

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
آپ کی اپنی جماعت پاکستان پیپلز پارٹی ہمیشہ عوامی قوتوں کے ساتھ رہے گی۔ یہ قوتیں یہاں کے مزدور، کسان، طالب علم اور غریب لوگ ہیں۔ یہی اس ملک کے نمائندے ہیں۔ ہم سرمایہ داروں اور ان کے گماشتوں کے خلاف لڑ رہے ہیں اور مجھے یقین ہے کہ آپ عوام کی فتح آخری ہوگی عوام کی جنگ اس وقت تک جاری رہے گی جب تک کہ یہ ٹولہ اپنا جاہل براندہ تسلط کھونہیں بیٹھتا وہ ملک کی تقدیر کے مالک ہے۔	Your own party, Pakistan People’s Party, will always be with the public forces. These forces are the labourers, farmers, students, and the poor people from here. These very people are the representatives of this country. We are fighting against the capitalists and their cat’s paws, And I believe that the ultimate success will be of the masses. The battle of the masses against the certain minority of capitalists and their followers will be till the time, unless this group loses its cruel dominance. They are the master of the fate of the country.	Created identity. Created identity. Metaphor (people are called force) Art of spin. Use of pronoun & Metaphor. Use of pronoun. Exploitation of language. Exploitation of language. Power of language Created identity.

“Language is a primarily human and non-instinctive method of communicating ideas, emotions and desires by means of a system of voluntarily produced symbols” Sapir (1921).

In Chrisholm (1911) Vol. 13 Language is defined as

“A system of conventional, spoken or written symbols by means of which human beings, as members of social group and participants in its culture, communicate”

Language is the species specific and species uniform possession of man. It is present every-where in our thoughts and dreams, tears and laughter, prayers and meditations, relations and communication, utterance and silence. The power of language is very effective. Sweet (1900) says,

“Language may be defined as the expression of thought by means of speech sounds”

So, language is a weapon and we must use it in an apt way otherwise the power of language can destroy us and words can slap our face and punch our body.

“Power is more than an authoritative voice in decision making; its strongest form may well be the ability to define social reality, to impose visions of the world. Such visions are inscribed in language and enacted in interaction” Gal (1991).

5.6. Hegemony

According to Strinati (2014) fundamentally the Dominant groups in society, not exclusively the ruling class, maintain their dominance with the 'spontaneous consent' of the subordinate groups, including the working class, through the negotiated construction of a political and ideological consensus which incorporates both dominant and dominated groups.

“Power refers to the attempt by dominant groups in society to win the consent of subordinate groups and to achieve compromise equilibrium in ruling over them” Gramsci (1971a).

5.7. Ideology

According to the Oxford advanced learner’s dictionary ideology is, “A set of beliefs especially one held by a particular group that influences the way people behave” Sally Wehmeier (2009)⁴. Althusser (1971b), the follower of Marx, was the first person who elaborated the concept of ideology. Althusser (1971b) in his book “Ideology & Ideological State Apparatuses” writes that language is a source to project an ideology to govern individuals by the ideological state

⁴ Oxford Advanced Learner’s

apparatuses, which is in the interest and benefit of the ruling class. These ideological state apparatuses are the shrines, holy places, schools, family, the political system, the law, trade union, the media, culture and tradition. Politicians always depend upon language to express ideology. "Ideologies are primarily located in the unsaid (implicit propositions)." Fairclough (1998).

Original Text	Content	Item Analysis
یہ ملک انہی لوگوں کا ہے اور یہی اس کی تقدیر کے مالک ہیں ناکہ چند لوگ۔ یقین کیجیے بالآخر فتح عوام کی ہوگی۔ عوامی فتح کو دنیا کی کوئی طاقت نہیں روک سکتی۔ ملک کی اکثریت کس حال میں ہے؟	This country belongs to these people and they are the owner of its destiny, nor a few people. Be assured, the ultimate triumph will be of the masses. No power of the world can stop people's triumph. What is the condition of the majority of the country.....?	Hegemony. Hegemony. Political strategy (future hope). Universal reality. Hegemony. Exploitation Emotional Urge Hegemony
Original Text	Translation	Researcher's Finding
ایسا معاشی نظام ہی سب کے لیے مساوات قائم کر سکتا ہے ایک ترقی پذیر ملک جو اندرونی اور بیرونی استحصال کا شکار ہو اس کی راہ نجات سوشلزم میں ہے۔	Such economic system can set up equality for all the people Any developing country which has been exploited internally & externally can get liberty through socialism.	Bhutto's philosophy in favour of socialism. Projection of ideology in Favour of socialism.

Implicitly the ideology is used to enhance the interest of a specific class and not of the common class. So, one aspect of ideology is quite vivid and important here that ideology is never projected in explicit form but always in implied form. Ideology can also be considered as a system of meanings and values. The form in which consciousness is at once expressed and controlled, as Raymond Williams has defined it: "...a mistaken interpretation of how the world actually is." Williams (1992).

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this article provides a vivid and profound insight to understand the political speeches and their language. The present study presents the devices Pakistani politicians use through language and get their objectives while employing Emotional exploitation, Repetition of Three-word theory, Art of spin, linguistic choices like sister like relationship, use of Personal pronoun, metaphor, and language as a power to express their Ideology. The study throws light on the fact that the politicians and specially seasoned ones are well versed in handling the situation with the help of language.

References

- Althusser, L. (1971a). Ideology and state ideological apparatuses. *Lenin and philosophy and other essays*, 121-176.
 Althusser, L. (1971b). Ideology and the State. *Lenin and philosophy and other essays*, 2.
 Atkinson, J. W. (1983). *Personality, Motivation, and Action: Selected Papers*: Praeger Publishers.
 Atkinson, K., & Atkinson, D. (2003). *Language and power in the modern world*: Edinburgh University Press.
 Beard, A. (2000). *The language of politics*: Psychology Press.
 Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Politeness: Some universals in language usage* (Vol. 4): Cambridge university press.

- Bull, P., & Fetzer, A. (2006). Who are we and who are you? The strategic use of forms of address in political interviews. *Text & Talk-An Interdisciplinary Journal of Language, Discourse Communication Studies*, 26(1), 3-37.
- Chilton, P. (2004). *Analysing political discourse: Theory and practice*: Routledge.
- Chilton, P., & Schäffner, C. (1997). Discourse and politics. *Discourse as social interaction*, 2, 206-230.
- Crisholm, H. (1911). *The Encyclopædia britannica: a dictionary of arts, sciences, literature and general information* (Vol. 29): At the University press.
- Crystal, D. (1991). A dictionary of phonetics and linguistics.
- De Landtsheer, C. (1998). Introduction to the study of political discourse. O. Feldman ve C. De Landtsheer (der.) Politically speaking.(ss. 1-18): Westport: Praeger.
- Duszak, A. (2002). *Us and others: Social identities across languages, discourses and cultures* (Vol. 98): John Benjamins Publishing.
- Fairclough, N. (1998). Political discourse in the media: An analytical framework. *Approaches to media discourse*, 142-162.
- Fairclough, N. (2000). Discourse, social theory, and social research: The discourse of welfare reform. *Journal of Sociolinguistics*, 4(2), 163-195.
- Fairclough, N. (2001). *Language and power*: Pearson Education.
- Foucault, M. (1980). *Language, counter-memory, practice: Selected essays and interviews*: Cornell University Press.
- Gal, S. (1991). Between speech and silence. *Gender at the crossroads of knowledge: Feminist anthropology in the postmodern era*, 175-203.
- Gastil, J. (1992). Undemocratic discourse: A review of theory and research on political discourse. *Discourse & Society*, 3(4), 469-500.
- Gibbs Jr, R. W. (1994). Figurative thought and figurative language.
- Goatly, A. (1997). A response to Schleppegrell: What makes a grammar green? *Journal of Pragmatics*, 28(2), 249-251.
- Gramsci, A. (1971a). *Hegemony*: na.
- Gramsci, A. (1971b). Selections from the Prison Notebooks, ed. and trans. Quintin Hoare and Geoffrey Nowell Smith: New York: International Publishers.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1978). *Language as social semiotic: The social interpretation of language and meaning*: Hodder Arnold.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1994). Language as social semiotic. *Language and literacy in social practice*, 23-43.
- Harris, Z. S. (1957). Co-occurrence and transformation in linguistic structure. *Language*, 33(3), 283-340.
- Hobbes, T. (1962). 1651/1962. *Leviathan*: New York: Collier Books.[16].
- Hornby, A. S. (2007). *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* (New 7th edition): London, Oxford University.
- Koller, V. (2003). Metaphor clusters, metaphor chains: Analyzing the multifunctionality of metaphor in text.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980a). Conceptual metaphor in everyday language. *The journal of Philosophy*, 77(8), 453-486.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980b). The metaphorical structure of the human conceptual system. *Cognitive science*, 4(2), 195-208.
- Mills, S. (2002). *Rethinking politeness, impoliteness and gender identity* (Vol. 89): 69J.
- Norman, F. (1989). *Language and power*. London and New York: Longman.
- Nunan, D. (1992). *Collaborative language learning and teaching*: Cambridge University Press.
- O'Leary, Z. (2005). *Researching real-world problems: A guide to methods of inquiry*: Sage.
- Sapir, E. (1921). 1949. *Language: an Introduction to the Study of Speech*.
- Strinati, D. (2014). *An introduction to studying popular culture*: Routledge.
- Sweet, H. (1900). *The history of language*: Dent.
- Ujin, Z. A., & Goundi, F. S. (1988). *Bhutto Ki Awaz*.
- Williams, R. (1992). The metropolis and the emergence of modernism. *Modernism/Postmodernism*, 82-94.
- Wilson, J. (1990). *Politically speaking: The pragmatic analysis of political language*: Basil Blackwell.